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ABSTRACTS

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Extraction of silica from Rice Straw and applications in wastewater treatment

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Abstract: Silica, which is an elementary mineral, has numerous applications in a wide range of fields including scientific, industrial as well as biological. In the field of science, the adaptability of silica is employed for its catalytic properties, greatly contributing to the growth of chemical research and catalysis. Silica finds its application from materials used in construction to manufacturing of ceramics and glass, unveiling its pivotal role in the development of modern infrastructure. Furthermore, silica has emerged as a major player in cell processes with the potential to affect structural integrity of cells and organisms under biological conditions. This research is aimed at extracting silica from Rice Straw Ash, an agricultural waste product that is produced in large quantities globally. This was characterized using Scanning Electron Microscope, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy, X-Ray Diffraction, Brunauer–Emmett–Teller surface area, point of zero charge, and moisture content. The extracted product was then used for adsorption testing of a diazo dye, an industrial effluent that is harmful to the environment, and cancerous to humans. The Pure sample was found to remove approximately 75 % of dye at a dose of 0.8 grams. The optimum time for this removal was 1 hour 15 minutes. Further research is required for various dyes to understand the adsorption properties of silica. The importance of silica is reinforced by its use in environment applications, where it helps to eliminate pollutants and contributes to the development of sustainable technologies.

Keywords: Silica, Rice straw, Adsorption, dye, Chacterization

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